

EFFECTIVE APPLICATION OF ECONOMETRIC MODELING METHODS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF EXPORTS OF FRUITS AND VEGETABLES

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and vegetables

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Abstract. *In this article, the state of fruit and vegetable exports in our country was studied, and the data obtained on factors affecting the export of fruit and vegetable products were analyzed using mathematical and statistical methods. The quality of the forecast of the obtained model was assessed and conclusions were drawn on the further development of this area based on the results of the analysis.*

Keywords: *agricultural products, fruit and vegetable products exposition, result factor, factors affecting, correlation coefficient, regression equation parameters, multicollenarity, econometric model, model evaluation.*

Introduction

Horticulture occupies a special place in ensuring the welfare of the population and the food security of the country. The existing conditions for the development of the industry in Uzbekistan make it possible to produce products of the industry in much larger quantities than what will be sufficient to meet the country's domestic needs. High competitiveness of export-oriented products can also be achieved. Because the natural and climatic conditions of our country, the labour potential of the industry, and the economic and organizational conditions that contribute to the development of the industry are sufficient.

Agriculture is one of the main sectors of the economy and requires increased attention due to the fact that most of the population in rural areas is employed in this area, and that, as a result of agricultural exports, a healthy balance of trade and foreign exchange reserves can be maintained. After all, international trade not only leads to increased productivity but also increases the level of employment in countries, thus making it possible to participate in the global economy. This leads to the stimulation of economic growth.

President Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, in his "Message to the Oliy Majlis" dated December 29, 2020, also noted that "the fight against poverty will be the main economic issue of 2021. The most rapidly developing factor in reducing poverty and increasing the incomes of the rural population is a sharp increase in productivity and efficiency in agriculture ...".¹

Therefore, a variety of measures are planned to grow this industry and boost exports, and entrepreneurs are given advantages and financial support. The government of our nation has implemented reforms in this area with the goal of raising the productivity of a significant sector of the economy—agriculture—by introducing new technologies, conserving resources, accelerating the process of further processing, and boosting the price of export-oriented goods.

Analysis of literature on the topic

Science In the past ten years, econometrics has made significant scientific progress, and the range of research and scientific work that employs econometric and economic-mathematical approaches is continuously expanding. The fact that numerous economists, including R. Fridzh and J. Tinberg (1969), L. Klein (1980), T. Haavelmo (1989), J. Heckman and D. McFadden (2000),

J. Angrist and G. Imbens (2021), have received the prestigious Nobel Prize in their field of study is proof that econometrics is recognised and studied by scientists all over the world.

According to the definitions of illustrious scientists provided in the book "Econometrics" by N.Sh. Kremer and B.A.Putko, we gain an understanding of the numerous interpretations of econometrics. According to definitions, one of the fields of economics devoted to the creation and use of statistical techniques for determining the relationship between economic variables is econometrics (S. Fischer and others). The primary goal of econometrics is to add empirical support to economic reasoning (L. Klein). The aim of econometrics is to derive economic laws empirically (E. Malenvo). When studying the economic environment in which we live, econometrics serves as both a telescope and a microscope (C. Griliches). According to S.A. Ayvazyan, econometrics integrates a number of techniques and models that allow qualitative relationships based on economic theory, economic statistics, and mathematical statistics to have quantitative representations. [2]

In his textbook "Econometrics," V.P. Nosko states: "Econometrics is a set of procedures for analysing the correlations between various economic indicators (factors) based on real statistical data." This methodology uses mathematical statistics and probability theory as its tools. These techniques can be used to detect new, previously undiscovered correlations between economic indicators, disprove various assumptions concerning the presence of certain relationships between economic indicators put forth by economic theory, and forecast future values of economic indicators. One of the main areas of study in contemporary economics, along with microeconomics and macroeconomics, is econometrics. To analyse statistical data, econometrics use mathematical statistics and probability theory techniques. But although some models and techniques are more frequently employed in macro-level research, others are more frequently used in micro-level study. [3]

The textbook "Econometrics" by I.I. Eliseeva et al. gives a brief historical overview of the origins and progress of econometrics, discusses coupled regression from the perspective of econometric analysis, i.e., the particulars of the regression equation and its correspondence to the original data, discusses the properties of residuals, and illustrates the potential using straightforward econometric tests. The situation of using spatial data and all the issues that arise in this case are also taken into consideration in the presentation of econometric modelling, which corresponds to the nature of economic processes and phenomena, first and foremost: non-linearity of efficiency, multicollinearity of variables, and heteroscedasticity of random residuals. [4]

When we look at studies from other countries, we also notice that the demand for fruits and vegetables is rising significantly on a global scale. Because of the rise in the import of fruits like grapes, melons, citrus fruits, apples, and others in developed countries, we are now seeing a thorough investigation of this issue. [6] The extension of developing nations' exports into rich nations' markets will boost both the number of their more developed trading partners and global economic expansion. Research is being conducted on a large group of professionals in the food industry in both developed and developing countries. This research is being done for many people in the fields of agriculture, export, and trade, as well as to further enrich the diets of developed countries, ensure diversity and security in the world food supply, and achieve a sustainable level of diversification of trade in fruits and vegetables from developing countries to developed countries.

Research Methodology

Data from the State Statistics Committee and experimental estimates of transport costs based on the findings of an expert survey were used to explore the effects of fruit and vegetable production volumes and transport costs on the volume of fruit and vegetable exports. [5] For the relationship between the volume of fruit and vegetable output in the republic and transport expenses, an econometric model has been created. The parameters of the linear regression equation were established using the least squares approach, and a correlation analysis was completed between the model's contributing elements. The econometric analysis of the republic's exports of fruit and vegetable products utilises statistical data from 2011 through 2020.

Despite the fact that the share of agriculture in the total volume of gross domestic product tends to decrease, there are high growth rates of agricultural products. In particular, in 2021, the volume of agricultural production increased 1.4 times compared to 2019, amounting to 317781.6 billion. soums, including crop production, reached 151083.4 trillion. sum, livestock products – 151441.5 trillion. sum . In the structure of GDP, the share of agriculture, forestry and fisheries in 2021 amounted to 26.9%. This year, the growth rate of products (services) of agriculture, forestry and fisheries, compared with the corresponding period in 2020, amounted to 104.0%, including in crop production – 103.4% and animal husbandry – 102.1%.

Analysis and results

The majority of the focus on this subject in our nation is producing outcomes. Despite the pandemic's detrimental effects, exports of fruits and vegetables reached USD \$1 billion in 2020. (Figure 1). The State Statistics Committee states that even if exports of fruits and vegetables slightly decline in 2020 as a result of the epidemic, overall exports have increased in recent years. The sector, however, is concentrating on supply chains, infrastructure, market penetration into Europe, and production that is export-oriented.

Figure 1. The volume of exports of fruits and vegetables (million US dollars)²

An examination of agricultural indicators for the production of fruits and vegetables reveals that the sector had significant increase beginning in 2016. (Fig. 2). Naturally, this is promising because it means that there will be an abundance of food on the home market, more people will be working in agriculture, and so on. Studying how this issue affects the rise in exports of fruits and vegetables is also crucial.

Figure 2. Volume of fruit and vegetable production (billion sum)³

It makes use of statistical data that affects the amount of fruit and vegetable product production (X1) (SSCom data), transport costs (X2) (experimental direct transport costs based on the findings of an expert poll), and the amount of fruit and vegetable product export (Y).

It is feasible to create plans and recommendations for the further development of the sector after determining the impact of these aspects. First, in order to determine the relationship between the resulting component and the influencing factors, the correlation coefficient is examined (Table 1).

**Table 1
Correlation coefficient between factors⁴**

	y	x1	x2
y	1		
x1	-0,3813	1	
x2	0,966446	-0,40263	1

The table reveals a very tight connection between the second influencing factor and the resultant factor, which is below the inverse average for the first influencing component. Given that there is no multicollinearity among the contributing elements, it is clear from the statistical data analysis that the cost of transportation directly affects the export of fruits and vegetables.

It is necessary to create a linear regression equation in the plural of the following form in order to explore the relationships between the components that have been analyzed:

$$y = a_0 + a_1 * x_1 + a_2 * x_2 + \dots + a_n x_n \quad (1)$$

Where y is the resulting factor, x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n - influencing factors and $a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ - regression equation parameters. Using the least squares method, it will be possible to determine the parameters of the regression equation using the following system of normal equations:

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